

Titanium (IV) Complexes with 8-Quinolinol*

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Dialkoxybis-(8 quinolinolato)titanium(IV) chelates have been prepared and studied. Titanoxane polymers were obtained by the hydrolysis of the dialkoxy-bis (8 quinolinolato)titanium(IV), as also of the reaction product of titanium tetrachloride with 8 quinolinol. Absorption bands due to alkoxy groups were absent in the infrared spectra of the hydrolysis products of the dialkoxy compounds. Strong and broad bands at ca. 825 cm^{-1} and at ca. 735 cm^{-1} ascribable to Ti-O-Ti stretching frequency were observed in the spectra of the hydrolysis products.

During the course of the preparation of inorganic polymers with bis (8-hydroxy-5-quinolyl)-methane¹, a ligand soluble in dimethylformamide (DMF) only, difficulties were experienced in removing the DMF which was retained tenaciously by the polymer. It was, therefore, thought desirable to study simple systems with 8-quinolinol itself.

Although oxo bis (8-quinolinolato) titanium (IV) dihydrate is known for a long time, search of literature revealed that the compound was not examined thoroughly. Berg and Teitelbaum² reported that quantitative precipitation of the orange yellow complex, $\text{TiO}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ takes place in slightly acid or alkaline medium. Early workers³⁻⁵ studied the reactions of tetravalent titanium and 8-quinolinol from the stand point of estimation of titanium only. Thermogravimetric studies carried out by Borrel and Paris⁶ and by Duval⁷ contradicted the results of Berg and Teitelbaum². Thus, according to Borrel and Paris⁶, the compound containing two molecules of water was not stable and loss of water occurred at temperatures of $40-50^\circ$. On the other hand, Duval⁷ stated that the anhydrous complex was formed at temperatures in the region of 115° and at this temperature, it was comparatively stable.

Attempts made in this investigation to obtain anhydrous oxo bis (8-quinolinolato)-titanium(IV) were not successful. Various polymeric products containing presumably Ti-O-Ti linkage were obtained. Attempts were also made to obtain titanoxane polymers by the hydrolysis of dialkoxybis-(8-quinolinolato) titanium(IV). However, search of literature revealed that Takimoto and Rust⁸ had isolated diisopropoxy bis (8-quinolinolato)-titanium(IV) and obtained anhydrous $\text{TiO}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON})_2$, by the hydrolysis of the alkoxy-compound. But the work reported here shows that the hydrolysed product

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contains one water molecule, $\text{TiO}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. Furthermore, the products obtained from diethoxy-, diisopropoxy, and dibutoxy bis (8-quinolinolato)-titanium(IV) chelates and the hydrolysis product from the reaction of titanium tetrachloride and 8-quinolinol, are the same as judged from their analyses and their infrared spectra.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solvents used for these preparations were purified and dried according to known methods. 8-Quinolinol was of Riedel-deHaën, C. P. grade. Titanium tetraalkoxides were prepared according to the procedures described by Bradley and co-workers⁹⁻¹¹.

T.G.A. Determined in a balance using McBain-Bakr type Quartz-spring¹².

V.P.C. Recorded on Aerograph A 350B with hydrogen as carrier gas, column P, temperature 70°.

Reaction between titanium tetrachloride and 8-quinolinol: 8-Quinolinol (14.5 g; 0.1 mole) dissolved in benzene (75 ml.) was added slowly to titanium tetrachloride (9.5 g; 0.05 mole) in benzene (50 ml.) placed in a two-necked flask fitted with a stirrer and a reflux condenser. A bright red compound was immediately formed which was kept under mild reflux for one hour and a half before the compound was collected on a filter. It was washed with several portions of benzene and dried.

This product (1.0 g) was hydrolysed by keeping in contact with water (150 ml.) for 48 hr. The bright yellow product thus obtained was filtered and dried at 110° for 2 hr. (Product A). Found: C, 59.00; H, 3.47; Ti, 13.57%. Calculated for $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O}_7\text{Ti}_2$, C, 59.89; H, 3.63; Ti, 13.27%.

The above product was recrystallised from absolute alcohol (Product B). Found: C, 61.39; H, 3.43; N, 7.96; Ti, 13.6%. Calculated for $\text{C}_{72}\text{H}_{50}\text{N}_8\text{O}_{13}\text{Ti}_4$: C, 60.63; H, 3.53; N, 7.86; Ti, 13.44%.

Reaction between titanium tetraethoxide and 8-quinolinol: To a solution of titanium tetraethoxide (2.28 g; 0.01 mole) in benzene (30 ml.) was added over a period of 25 minutes, 8-quinolinol (2.9 g; 0.2 moles) in benzene (40 ml.). Orange-yellow solution was formed immediately. The solvent and the liberated alcohol were removed under reduced pressure. An orange-yellow solid was obtained. Yield, 4.0 g (93.9%). Found: C, 62.53; H, 4.98; N, 6.20; Ti, 11.24%. Calculated for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Ti}$: C, 62.03; H, 5.21; N, 6.58; Ti, 11.25%.

To 1.1 g of diethoxy bis (8-quinolinolato)-titanium (IV) was added 5-10 ml. of water. The crystals were filtered and dried to give 0.70 g of yellow amorphous powder (Product C). Found: C, 57.12; H, 4.17; Ti, 12.20; N, 7.8. Calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Ti}$: C, 58.38; H, 3.81; Ti, 12.94; N, 7.60%.

Reaction between titanium tetraisopropoxide and 8-quinolinol: Similarly, from titanium tetraisopropoxide (2.84 g; 0.01 mole) in benzene (30 ml.) and 8-quinolinol (2.9 g; 0.02 mole)

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in benzene (50 ml.) the diisopropoxy compound was prepared. Lemon yellow solid. Yield, 4.29 (94.5%). Found: C, 63.34; H, 4.93, N, 6.57; Ti, 10.32%. Calculated for $C_{24}H_{26}O_4N_2Ti$: C, 63.48; H, 5.77; N, 6.17; Ti, 10.54%. This product was hydrolysed as before (Product D). Found: C, 57.12; H, 4.17; Ti, 12.20; N, 7.85%.

Reaction between titanium tetrabutoxide and 8-quinolinol: This reaction was carried out in a three-necked flask provided with a high speed vacuo-stirrer and a pear-bulb fractionating column connected through a take-off condenser to a receiver for the alcohol evolved during the reaction. The quantities of the reagents were 1.99 g (0.007 mole) of n-butyl titanate in 25 ml. of dry benzene and 2.04 g (0.014 mole) of 8-quinolinol in 100 ml. dry xylene. As heating, stirring and distillation of alcohol proceeded, the solution acquired a red colour. Benzene solution of n-butyl titanate was added slowly while stirring was continued during a period of half an hour. Benzene and butyl alcohol were distilled off quantitatively. (The V.P.C. showed that the quantity of butyl alcohol collected into the distillate was 1.12 g; theoretical value is 1.04 g). The mixture was cooled and 2.1 ml. of water and 50 ml. of dry petroleum ether (40-60°) were added with stirring. The hydrolysis product was collected on a filter under suction, dried under vacuum, immediately recrystallised from absolute alcohol and dried. Yield 2.0 g; (77.2%). (Product E). Found: C, 58.56; H, 3.71; N, 7.90; Ti, 12.44; Calculated for $C_{18}H_{14}O_4N_2Ti$: C, 58.38; H, 3.81; N, 7.60; Ti, 12.94%.

Dibutoxy-bis (8-quinolinolato) titanium (IV) was isolated by the addition of petroleum ether (40-60°) to a small portion of the reaction mixture. The solid separated was collected on a filter, washed with a little petroleum ether and dried under vacuum. Found Ti, 10.10%; Calculated for $C_{26}H_{30}O_4N_2Ti$, Ti, 9.94%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Attempts to obtain anhydrous TiO (C_9H_6ON)₂ by drying oxo bis-(8-quinolinolato) titanium(IV) dihydrate at 110° were unsuccessful. Prolonged drying results in slight decomposition of the product and at the same time water is not completely removed as shown by the presence of a medium intense band at ca. 3500 cm^{-1} . in the infrared spectrum of the dried product. Hence the compound was dried at 110° for 2 hr. only (Product A) and was recrystallised from absolute alcohol (Product B). On the basis of elemental analysis, the product B can be formulated as anhydrous oxo bis-(8-quinolinolato)-titanium(IV), $TiO(C_9H_6ON)_2$. But the infrared spectrum (fig. 1) of this product showed bands at 3450 cm^{-1} (OH stretching) and at ca. 1600 cm^{-1} (OH bending) indicating the presence of OH groups. The presence of OH groups in the spectrum together with the presence of strong and broad bands at ca. 825 cm^{-1} and at ca. 735 cm^{-1} suggests polymeric structure for the complex perhaps of the type (I) when the value of $n=1$, the elemental analysis for compound A agrees well with the above formulation. Similarly for the compound B, the values agree when $n=3$.

where Ox stands for C_9H_6ON ,

The dialkoxybis-(8-quinolinolato) titanium (IV) complexes turn to yellow amorphous powders on addition of water. The change may be ascribed to the hydrolysis of unstable alkoxy groups and subsequent condensation with the formation of polymeric substances with Ti-O-Ti bonds.¹³ Thermal analysis of the hydrolysed product showed that the compound is stable up to 280° and rapid decomposition starts from 300° onwards (fig. 2). The limited solubility precluded the determination of molecular weight of the hydrolyses products.

The infrared absorption maxima in nujol mull of oxo-bis-(8-quinolinolato) titanium (IV) complexes are given in table I.

TABLE I

Infrared absorption frequencies (cm⁻¹) in nujol mull of bis(8-quinolinolato) titanium(IV) complexes

8-Quinolinol	Product A	Product B	Product C	Product D	Product E	Possible assignments
3350b, m	3350m	3450m	3400m, b	3450m, b	3425m	OH str.
2900*b, vs	2950*b, vs 1650v. w	2905*b, vs 1640w	2900*b, vs 1670w 1640m	2900*b, vs 1650m	2950*b, vs 1650w	
	1600v. w	1600m	1600m	1600m	1600m	OH bend
1582s	1570s	1572s	1570s	1575s	1570s	C=N str.
1508vs	1490s	1500vs	1495vs	1500vs	1495vs	
1466*b, vs	1450*vs	1480*vs	1450*vs	1470*vs	1470*vs	
1415s						OH in-plane def.
1377s*	1370*vs 1317s	1370*vs 1322vs	1370*vs 1317vs	1375*vs 1317vs	1375*vs 1320vs	
1291sh						
1279vs	1270s	1275s	1260s	1267s	1265s	benzene and pyridine ring vibrn.
1288vs	1225w	1228m	1225m	1225w	1220w	
1205vs, b						
1176sh	1175w	1170w	1170m	1175w	1175w	
1166s						
1139s						
1094s	1100s	1100vs	1100vs	1100vs	1100vs	C—O—str.
1061s		1050m	1050w			
	1025w	1028m	1028m	1025w	1025w	
975s						
898s						O-H out of plane def.
867m		884m	860w			
821b, s	820vb, vs	839vb, vs	820vb, vs	820vb, vs	833vb, s	Ti-O-Ti str
808sh	805sh	805sh		805sh	805sh	
785b, s	790sh	782s	780s	780m	780m	
743b, s	753vb, s	730vb, vs	740vb, vs	735vb, vs	733vb, vs	Ti-O-Ti str
711b, s						

*Nujol peaks

s, strong; m, medium; w, weak; v, very; b, broad; sh, shoulder.

13. A. Yamamoto and S. Kambara, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 4344.

In the spectra of oxobis-(8-quinolinolato) titanium(IV) complexes, there is no band corresponding to Ti=O in the region of 900-1100 cm^{-1} expected for titanyle compounds¹⁴. Instead, strong and broad bands are observed at ca. 825 cm^{-1} and at ca. 735 cm^{-1} . The hydrolyses products obtained from dialkoxybis-(8-quinolinolato)-titanium(IV) complexes also show broad bands at ca. 735 cm^{-1} and at ca. 825 cm^{-1} and show no bands corresponding to Ti=O. Giddings¹⁵, Zeitler and Brown¹⁶, and Nyholm and his co-workers¹⁴ have assigned the bands at ca. 730 cm^{-1} and at ca. 830 cm^{-1} in titanyle compounds to Ti-O-Ti stretching frequency. As the Table I shows, 8-quinolinol also has strong bands at ca. 821 cm^{-1} and at ca. 734 cm^{-1} . Close observation of the spectra shows that the bands at ca. 735 cm^{-1} and at ca. 825 cm^{-1} in bis(8-quinolinolato) titanium(IV) complexes are more broad and strong. The broadening of these bands may be ascribed to the overlapping of Ti-O-Ti stretching frequencies with those of chelated 8-quinolinol. The C=N stretching frequency somewhat coupled with pyridine ring vibration, appears as a strong band in 8-quinolinol¹⁷ at 1582 cm^{-1} and is lowered on chelation to ca. 1570 cm^{-1} . The other bands in the region from ca. 1470 cm^{-1} to ca. 1600 cm^{-1} arise mainly from C=C stretching vibrations. The C-O stretching frequency at C-O-M site discussed by some investigators¹⁸ is shifted from 1094 cm^{-1} in the ligand to 1100 cm^{-1} in the chelates as expected.

The strong band present at 1415 cm^{-1} in the ligand and absent in the chelates, can be assigned to the phenolic OH in plane deformation, the OH out of plane deformation is apparent at 898 cm^{-1} in the ligand. The bands at 1279, 1166, 1139 cm^{-1} are characteristic vibrations of the ligand. Similar characteristic vibrations are observed for substituted pyridine ring¹⁹.

The infrared absorption frequencies (cm^{-1}) in nujol mull of dialkoxy-bis (8-quinolinolato) titanium(IV) complexes are given in table II.

TABLE II

Infrared absorption frequencies (cm^{-1}) in nujol mull of dialkoxy-bis (8-quinolinolato) titanium(IV) complexes.

$\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2(\text{Ox})_2$	$\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)_2(\text{Ox})_2$	$\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)_2(\text{Ox})_2$
2900*b,vs	2900*b, vs	2900*b, vs
1570s	1590w	1590s
1500s	1570s	
	1500s	1520s
1450*s	1450*s	1480*s
1367*s	1367*s	1380*s
1317s	1317s	1340s
1267m	1267s	1280s
	1217m	1240m
		1180m

14. C. G. Barraclough, J. Lewis and R. S. Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 3552, (1959).

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18. R. G. Charles, H. Freiser, R. Friedel, L. E. Hillard and W. D. Johnston, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1956, **8**, 1.

19. H. Shindo, *Pharm. Bull.*, 1957, **5**, 472.

TABLE II (Contd.)

Ti (OC ₂ H ₅) ₂ (Ox) ₂	Ti (OC ₃ H ₇) ₂ (Ox) ₂	Ti (OC ₄ H ₉) ₂ (Ox) ₂
1106s	1136s	
	1124s	1120s
	1100s	1100sh
	1050w	
1060b, m	1010sh	1040m
	1000s	
975w		980w
915m	850s	905w
825m	835m	835s
	820s	
	810m	810m
780m	795w	800b, m
	790m	
	775w	
745b, m	740b,s	750b, m
720b, m	720sh	

The infrared absorption spectrum of diisopropoxy bis(8-quinolinolato)-titanium(IV) showed two strong absorption bands at ca. 1000 cm⁻¹ and at ca. 1100 cm⁻¹. (fig. 3). The dibutoxy compound (Table II) showed a medium intense band at 1040 cm⁻¹, a broad shoulder at 1100 cm⁻¹ and a sharp and strong band at 1120 cm⁻¹, while the diethoxy compound showed absorption bands at 1060 cm⁻¹ (medium, broad) at 1106 cm⁻¹ (strong). The absorption bands in the region between 1000 cm⁻¹ and 1200 cm⁻¹ are considered to be characteristic of alkoxy groups¹³. In the hydrolysed products of these dialkoxy bis(8-quinolinolato) titanium (IV) compounds no band was found corresponding to the bands at ca. 1000 cm⁻¹ but the band at ca. 1100 cm⁻¹ remained intact. The other bands due to the chelate rings near 1570 cm⁻¹ and at 1500 cm⁻¹ also remained essentially the same. The bands at ca. 1000 cm⁻¹ in the dialkoxy compounds, therefore, may arise due to C-O stretching vibrations of the alkoxy group bound to a titanium atom and the bands at ca. 1100 cm⁻¹ due to the carbonyl stretching vibrations at the C-O-Ti site. In the metal chelates of 8-quinolinol, Charles and his co-workers¹⁸ have assigned the strong band at ca. 1100 cm⁻¹ to C-O stretching vibration frequencies at the C-O-M site. Takimoto and Rust⁸, however, assigned the bands in diisopropoxy chelated titanium compound between 1100 cm⁻¹ and 1160 cm⁻¹ to the isopropyl skeletal vibrations and the band at 1000 cm⁻¹ to a carbonyl group attached to the C-O-Ti linkage.

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